

ANALYSIS OF REGIONAL GOVERNMENT FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE, EVIDENCE FROM INDONESIA

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Abstract

The Purpose of this research is to test the impact of transparency and accountability to financial performance local government of Gorontalo. The Research approach used is an explanation with survey method of selecting the population of the organizational work device of the city of Gorontalo, with sample withdrawal using the purposive sampling method as many as 30 respondents. The exposure of an independent variable to the dependent variable using multiple regression analyses, data processing uses SPSS. Data analysis begins with testing the validity, reliability, and normality of each of the variables examined and subsequently conducted testing requirements of the classic assumption analysis test requirement consisting of a test multicollinearity, heterokedastisity test and autocorrelation. To test hypothesis carried out a partial T-test and simultaneous F test, a related Corps regression testand determination. The results showed that Transparency and accountability effect positively and significantly on financial performance, both in partial and simultaneous, with large contributions from variables Independent of dependent variables, therefore it's advisable that the attention to transparency and accountability increasingly get the attention of the government as a decision maker in order to increase the regional financial performance.

Keywords: Transparency, Accountability, Financial Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Government as an institution that is fully responsible for society or public, because the government has a duty to provide public services that can help the needs of the community. The Government also has objectives to be achieved that are poured in the form of targets and targets. The Government's success in achieving the target or target is a performance. Good governance performance is at least characterized by two elements namely transparency and accountability. Transparency in the wake of freedom

of obtaining information while accountability of public responsibility for every activity undertaken and entering the era of reform followed by the enactment of regional autonomy policies and Fiscal decentralization leads to a very fast growing public sector organization. The enactment of regional autonomy and fiscal decentralization in Indonesia requires each region to be able to conduct proper budget management. Appropriate management can be achieved if the local government is clever and careful in choosing the arrangement of working environment and accounting system that is good for its budget. Careful and precise selection can realize an accountable government in the performance of drafting its financial statements mentioning that the local government is given a broad authority to conduct its own financial management, as it All the rules and expectations of society is the realization of a transparent government and uphold public accountability, although now we feel it is still very difficult to prosecute the local government to provide information widely Accountability of its financial statements.

According (JITMAU1, 2013) the government will emphasize the government's accountability aspect in government bureaucracy reform. To realize Government accountability to its citizens one way is done using the principle of transparency (openness). Through the transparency of governance, the community is given the opportunity to know the policy that will be taken by the government. Also through transparency of governance, the community can provide feedback or outcomes to the policies that have been taken by the government. As with accountability, transparency also has an important influence in the government's military because with transparency, the community is given the opportunity to know the policies or decisions that have been established by Government. So, the government provides information needed by the public about the policies taken by the government.

The attention to the issue of transparency and accountability of public finance in Indonesia has increased in the last decade. This is largely due to the economic crisis and fiscal turbulent has contributed to the substantial erosion of public trust against the government in the state's financial management. And fiscal decentralization from the central government to local governments, as a consequence of regional autonomy, has led to significant changes in the composition of budget expenditures on central and local governments.

The annual report (financial statements), although it has not reported the overall accountability of government entities, is generally considered the primary media of accountability, (Aliyah, 2012) and opinion Other by Ryan et al. (2002) stating that there are two generally accepted objectives of the public sector's annual reporting that is accountability (accountability) and the decision usefulness (decision making).

The financial performance of local governments and public accountability can be realized by the implementation of effective functional supervision, in the local government there is a functional supervision authority of the government or a city that assists the leadership Government in conducting supervision whether activities undertaken by its apparatus in accordance with the vision, mission objectives and programs that determine the accountability purpose of providing and presenting some of the information needed and understood by Interested parties especially the community that identifies the

effectiveness of accounting information systems as a resource that can improve the timeliness of financial reporting of this research becomes more interesting to do, because The delay in completion of financial statements often occurs even in the lowest sphere of the community, as does its members consist of underprivileged communities. The late financial statements can be seen from the results of the performance assessment conducted each month by the economic facilitator, if the financial statement is completed and informed through five strategic places that can be known by the community less than the fifth of the month, it is said to be timely as the opposite of (Yulianti, 2015).

Sugiarto (2018) of this research titled Mainframe Government Accounting in order to build accountability, transparency and measurement of local government performance. To learn more about the government's financial accountability performance, especially the local government. To carry out the mandate of LAW 32 year 2004 on local government and LAW No. 33 year 2004 on financial balance between the central government and local governments, the rights and obligations arising from the region can be assessed with money that needs to be managed in the regional financial system. During this time the government is often regarded as a nest of inefficiencies, wastage, and source of funds leakage. Emerging demands for local governments consider the value of money considering inputs, results, and results together, which is believed to increase public sector accountability and improve public sector performance by increasing the effectiveness of Public services, improving the quality of public services, lowering public cost of services due to loss of inefficiencies, and raising awareness of public use of money. With the issuance of government regulation 24 years 2005 on government accounting standards should be a milestone in the birth of transparency, State participation and accountability in order to realize good governance. Such strategic measures are required that need to be pursued and implemented together in the framework of the implementation of government accounting standards.

Djtmau (2013) of this study titled Accountability Influence, transparency and internal audit function on local government performance (empirical study in Sorong Regency). In achieving good local government performance, accountability, transparency and good internal check function are also required for local government to be good quality and satisfactory. Thus, to solidify the accountability mechanism, good performance management is required. The application of various laws and regulations related to the implementation of the concept of accountability and transparency in financial management is expected to realize the management of local governments and parties to the people. Implementation of accountability and transparency in the financial management of the area is expected to improve local government performance.

Past studies taking the title of transparency implementation took in an effort to improve the quality of the financial report of the regional government's accountability and transparency in the financial management of Central and Areas as public sector organizations are an important objective of the public sector's accounting and administration reform. To be able to ensure that government financial management has been conducted by government apparatus, then the accountability and audit function of the public sector financial reporting should be well-done. Along with the demands of the

public sector organizations to improve the quality, professionalism and public accountability in carrying out their activities, audits are required not only limited to finance and compliance, but need to Audit of public sector performance. In the presence of transparency and accountability in financial statements, it will create a quality financial statement and the creation of good governance. Widilestariningtyas (2017)

With the decline in the financial performance of listed companies in East Africa and the rising trend of corporate failure in both global and local perspective. Stakeholders are increasingly becoming more concerned of the financial performance of their firms. This study aimed to find out whether corporate transparency disclosure can be used to address the decline in financial performance and corporate failures. Therefore, the current study sought to examine the influence of corporate transparency disclosure on financial performance among companies listed in East Africa. Specifically, the study sought to examine the influence of financial transparency, risk transparency, social transparency and governance transparency on financial performance of companies listed in East Africa. The study adopted both descriptive and correlation design. Purposive sampling was used to select the 65 listed companies in Nairobi securities exchange in Kenya, 16 companies quoted in Uganda securities exchange, 7 companies which are quoted in Rwanda Securities Exchange as well as 24 companies listed in Daresalaam securities exchange from 2006 to 2015. Secondary data was collected through the use of document check index retrieved from annual audited financial statements. Regression diagnostic and panel data diagnostic tests were carried out. Results of the study revealed that there was a positive and significant relationship between financial, governance, risk, social transparency and financial performance of listed companies in East Africa. Boniface. et all (2018)

Economic success of a country, if described in few words, is the success of big corporations of that country and vice versa. Corporate governance is thus economic governance in general. Some of the major corporate scandals that stunned global economies and businesses followed by falling down of corporate giants like Enron, BCCI, Coloroll, Polly Pech, Barings, HIH Insurance and Parmalat resulted in tight regulations, codes, and principles of corporate governance. These scandals erupted due to nonexistent of accountability and transparency principles of corporate governance within these companies as the management concealed important facts from the shareholders and that they were also not accountable for their actions.

This empirical research study intends to examine different characteristics of Corporate Governance and their impact on firm performance. These characteristics include Transparency and Accountability. Analyses were based on primary data which will be collected through questionnaire from 200 respondents. Correlation and Regression analysis were used to get results of the study. Results of the study revealed positive relationship between accountability and transparency with firm performance. The results showed that accountability and transparency has positive significant impact on the firm performance.⁽¹ Ullah at .all 2016)

The phenomenon on of the local government of Gorontalo still lack of transparency principle in providing information to the public with regard to the responsibility in the

submission of financial statements therefore the role of the government is very needed to increase transparency and accountability for the financial management of the regions in which the Government must be able to provide all relevant financial information that is honestly and openly open to the public. So that the resulting performance can be reaffirmed to the public. Based on that, the question that should be tested in relation to the variables studied is to allow transparency and accountability to influence the financial performance of the local government.

METHODOLOGY

The research approach used is explanation with Observation methods, interviews and quasi both quantitatively and qualitative, choosing the population of all the working devices of Gorontalo City's local government organization as much as 28 OPD. The exposure of an independent variable to the dependent variable using multiple regression analyses, data processing uses SPSS help. Data analysis begins by testing the validity and reliability of each of the variables studied which subsequently conducted testing requirements of the classical assumption test requirement consisting of a test of normality, multicollinearity, autocorrelation and Heterokedastisity test. To test hypothesis conducted partial T test and simultaneous F test as well as regression analysis testing

Variable relationships and measurement indicators can be addressed in the following table

Table 1: Variables and measurement indicators

Variables	Variable Concept	Indicator	Scale
Transparency (X1)	Transparency is the openness and it gives the place of active participations of all walks of life in the public resource process.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Willingness to access information 2. clarity in the provision of clear information 3. completeness in the provision of accurate documents 4. disclosure in the process of providing information 5. regulatory framework that guarantees Liker transparency 	Likert
Accountability (X2)	Accountability is functioning of all components of the Company's activities in accordance with their duties and authorities.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Accountability 2. Compliance 3. Avoidance 4. Policy 5. Liker Disclosure 	Likert
Financial performance (Y)	Financial performance is the determination of certain measures that can measure the success of an organization or company in	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Inclusion 2. Expenditure 3. revenue 4. Utilization of 5. Liker Policy 	Likert

RESULT'S

Validity test

Table 2: Transparency Validity Test Results

Question	R Count	R table	Caption
1	0,564	0,361	Valid
2	0,664	0,361	Valid
3	0,847	0,361	Valid
4	0,780	0,361	Valid
5	0,432	0,361	Valid

According to the Transparency Variable validity test table (X1), it can be concluded that all the item statements for each of the variables are declared valid. It can be seen from the value of R count on the total column for each question/statement on each variable > 0.361 this corresponds to its criteria if R count > 0.361 then the statement is said to be valid.

Table 3: Accountability Validity test Result

Question	R count	R table	Description
1	0,607	0,361	Valid
2	0,751	0,361	Valid
3	0,531	0,361	Valid
4	0,658	0,361	Valid
5	0,710	0,361	Valid

According to the accountability Variable validity test table (X2), it can be concluded that all the item statements for each of the variables are declared valid. It can be seen from the value of R count on the total column for each question/statement on each variable > 0.361 this corresponds to its criteria if R count > 0.361 then the statement is said to be valid.

Table 4: Financial performance Validity test results

Question	R count	R table	Description
1	0,463	0,361	Valid
2	0,699	0,361	Valid
3	0,782	0,361	Valid
4	0,782	0,361	Valid
5	0,519	0,361	Valid

The validity test of the financial performance variable (Y), concluded that all the items of the statement for each of the variables declared valid. It can be seen from the R count on the total column of each statement/statement on each variable > 0.361. This corresponds to Criteria if R counts > 0.361 then the statement is said to be valid.

According to the purpose of the validity test is to see how much the question/statement ability can find out the respondent's response. It can be concluded that all questions/statements posed by researchers in the questionnaire shared with the respondent can be used as an appropriate measuring instrument.

Reliability Test

Table 5: Reliability Testing Results

Variable	Test Results The Reliability	Crombach Alpha	Description
Transparency	0,654	0,600	Reliable
Accountability	0,659	0,600	Reliable
Financial Performance	0,651	0,600	Reliable

Table 5 shows the value of Cronbach's alpha which serves to test the reliability of the statements of each of the variables the researcher proposed. It is seen that the calculation results of Cronbach's alpha > 0.60 showing all the religious statements.

Classic Assumption Test

Test Data normality

Test normality aims to test whether in regression model, dependent and independent variables both have normal distribution or not test the normality of the data used in this study is the Kolmogorov – Smirnov test. One-sample test criteria using one-sided testing is by comparing the probability with a certain level of significance:

1. The significance value or probability of < 0.05 then the data distribution is not normal
2. Significance value or probability > 0.05 then normal data distribution.

Table 6: Test Normality One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		30
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	,0000000
	Std. Deviation	1,39787005
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	,112
	Positive	,095
	Negative	-,112
Test Statistic		,112
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		,200 ^{c,d}
a. Test distribution is Normal.		
b. Calculated from data.		
c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.		
d. This is a lower bound of the true significance		

Can be seen from the table above the significant value of 0.200 is greater than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the distributed data is normal. It is appropriate criteria if the value is significant or the probability > 0.05 then the distribution of data is normal.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 7: Multicollinearity Testing Coefficients^a

Model	Collinearity Statistics		Description
	Tolerance	VIF	
1	(Constant)		free multicollinearity
	Transparency	,985	
	Accountability	,985	

The proposed regression Model for variable Independen Everything is freed from this multicollinearity visible from the results of data processing indicating the independent variable has a Vif of < 10 so it can be concluded that this variable independent can be used to determine how it affects financial performance.

Heterokedastisity Test

This test aims to see if the regression model occurs variable inequality from the residual of one observation to another observation. If the variance of the residual one observation of the cloth remains, then it is called homokedastisity, and if different is called heterokedastisity. A good regression Model is not the case of heterokedastisity. In this study using Glessjer test is to see the significant value. > 0.05 it does not occur heterokedastisity.

Figure 1: Heterokedastisity Test

Based on the Scatterplot diagram above, the data is scattered randomly without forming a specific pattern of point spreading upwards and below on the Y No axis, this proves not to happen heterokedastisity. Thus it can be concluded that in this regression model there is a difference in the variance of the residual from an observation to another observation.

Regression coefficient (R) and determination (R²)

Analysis of Determine coefficients carried out to carry out a large present role of variable transparency accountability to financial performance

Table 8: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,709 ^a	,502	,465	1,449
a. Predictors: (Constant), accountability, transparency				
b. Dependent variables: financial performance				

The coefficient of determination is derived R number (correlation coefficient) of 0351. This indicates that there is a relationship between accountability transparency to financial performance.

Coefficient of determination (R²)

R² (Coefficient of determination is a value that shows the ability of Variable bound in this research R value obtained at 0709 which indicates that the financial performance of the existing regional government of Gorontalo especially in 10 OPD comparisons By variable Transparency Accountability is amounting to 70.9%.

Test T

A partial test (T-Test) is conducted to determine whether the Transparency variable of accountability is significantly positive for partial financial performance

Table 9: Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	-3,047	4,929		-,618	,542
Transparency	,478	,146	,446	3,263	,003
Accountability	,652	,147	,608	4,445	,000
a. Dependent Variable: financial performance					

The decision making criteria for accepting or rejecting hypotheses is by condition of:

If t count ≤ t table: H0 received or H1 rejected

If T count the table ≥ T: H0 rejected or H1 accepted

Table 9 shows T test results are:

- 1) Transparency has a positive and significant effect on partial financial performance. It is evidenced by the significant value of 0.003 is smaller than the significant value of 0.05 then it can be concluded that H0 rejected and H1 accepted
- 2) Accountability has a positive and significant effect on partial financial performance. It is evidenced by a significant 0.000 greater than the significant value of 0.05 then inferred H0 and H2 reject In the F test showed that there was a positive and significant influence on the variable transparency and accountability to the financial performance simultaneously as the following table 10:

Table 10: ANOVA^a

	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	57,199	2	28,600	13,627	,000 ^b
	Residual	56,667	27	2,099		
	Total	113,867	29			
a. Dependent Variable: financial performance						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Accountability, transparency						

Based on table 10 test result of ANOVA (analysis of Variance) obtained the value of F count (13.627) while the value of F table 10. Which means the value of F count is greater than the value of F table so it is proven that the variable X1 and X2 simultaneously positive To variable Y where HO rejects and H3 are accepted which means there is an influence between transparency and accountability to financial performance (Y).

Furthermore, of the significant value obtained (0.000) is smaller than the value (0.005) meaning that the regression model used is worth testing, this proves the better transparency and accountability will be jointly then the more Good financial performance. Based on table 9 output get regression equation model:

$$Y = -3,047 + 0,446X_1 + 0,608X_2$$

In the above regression equation, Constant (β_0) is amounting to -3,047 this means that without the existence of variable transparency (X1) and Accountability (X2) then the performance that occurred in the local government of Gorontalo City especially in the OPD of -3.047. While multiple regression test results for independent variables can be described as follows:

- 1) The value of the transparency coefficient (X1) of 0.446 is positively significant to performance (Y). This implies that one unit's transparency then the financial performance variable rises 44.6% assuming that the other independent variables remain.
- 2) Coefficient Value of accountability processing (X2) amounting to 0.608 positively affect (Y). This implies that every single unit of accountability increases the performance variables up by 60.8 assuming that the other independent variables remain

Hypothesis Testing

Based on a significant partial test result can be outlined the results of the following hypothesis testing:

1. Transparency (X1) positive and significant towards financial performance (Y)

The first hypothesis test reads transparency (X1) positive and significant towards financial performance (Y), the hypothesis tested is:

H0.1 = There is significant transparency over financial performance.

Ha.1 = There is significant transparency on financial performance.

Based on the calculation model of transparency regression coefficient of financial performance of 3.263 Sig 0.003 value smaller than $= 0.05$ because of the significant value greater than the value $= 0.05$ then the coefficient of transparency (X1) positively affects and to the financial performance (Y). Then this states that transparency has no positive and significant effect on financial performance (Y) is acceptable.

2. Effect of accountability (X2) is positive and significant towards financial performance (Y).

The second hypothesis test reads the management of Accountability (X2) is significant to the financial performance (Y). The hypotheses tested are:

H0.2 = There is significant accountability to financial performance

Ha.2 = There isn't significant accountability to financial performance

Based on the calculation of the model of accountability regression coefficient of the financial report of 4.445 sig value $= 0.00$ is smaller than value $= 0.05$, then the accountability coefficient (X2) is significant to the financial performance (Y). Then H03 states that accountability is significant to the financial performance (Y) received.

DISCUSSION

Effect of transparency (X1) on financial performance (Y)

Based on a partial test that has been carried out between transparencies (X1) to financial performance (Y) indicates that the T count of 3.263 with significant value ($0,003 < 0.05$) indicates that the variable transparency is positive and significant to the performance Financial. The results of these research trials are similar to previous hypotheses indicating that the influence of positive transparency on financial performance.

Based on the calculation of model of the transparency coefficient of financial performance of 0.446 sig value $= 0.003$ greater than value $= 0.05$ because of the significance value greater than the value

$= 0.05$, then the transparency regression coefficient (X1) has positive and significant effect on the financial performance (Y) received.

It is also shown by the value of coefficient of determination, namely with the value of R square of 0.709 that shows that 70.9% transparency has a significant positive influence on financial performance,

Here is the relationship indicator variable X1 (transparency to the Y variable (financial performance)).

1) Willingness and access to information

If the willingness to access the resulting information is accurate, timely, relevant and trustworthy, then the quantity and quality of work produced will be good. Likewise with timeliness and cooperation in completing when a fellow co-workers exchange reliable

information then everything that is done will have a good and timely results. Because human beings are social creatures it is important to always cooperate in doing work so that the results can be maximal.

2) Clarity in the provision of information

A clear clarity of information and detail will improve the perfection of the value of accurate and relevant information and can provide thorough information to the Community layer, especially in the supervision in 10 OPD Gorontalo City.

3) Completeness of providing information

Completing the provision of clear information about the procedure procedure is a sequence or steps to perform a work, task or activity procedure is a sequence or steps to conduct a work, task or Activities. And if the procedure that is in 10 OPD Gorontalo City is implemented then it will produce a good quantity and quality of work. Likewise, the problem of timeliness when the pickling follow the existing procedures then something that is done will be completed in time and of course this does not expire from the presence and cooperation of the group in solving it, because when the preservation is always is present on time and always follow the existing procedures then automatic what is done will result in something satisfactory and will have a good impact on the 10 offices. In 10 OPD that is in the case they always follow the procedure that there can be seen from the answer given through the questionnaire that was distributed researchers on 10 OPD Gorontalo City by giving an answer agree to the statement stated in the Questionnaires.

4) Disclosure Process

Disclosure of an information process that can access and improve transparency for local government, especially in 10 OPD of Gorontalo City.

5) Regulatory framework that guarantees open transparency and enhances the presence of open policies for supervision in order to produce healthy and tolerant political competition for the community.

Transparency is an earnest openness and gives the place of active participations from all walks of life in public resource processes. In the local government of the city must indeed have openness in general and can provide supervision and can have a well-accessible information provider (Saputra 2014)

The results of this study in line with the research conducted by Sugiarto (2018) of this research is a title of government Accounting in order to build accountability, transparency and performance measurement of the local government of Bandung. The results of this study indicate that partial transparency indicates that accountability has a performance effect on OPD. Simultaneous display of transparency has no effect on the performance of working units. And Ullah at.all 2016 too.

Accountability (X2) towards financial performance (Y).

Based on the partial test that has been conducted in accountability (X2) against financial performance (Y) shows T count 4.445 the significant value ($0,000 < 0.05$) indicates that accountability is positive and significant in respect to financial performance.

To see the magnitude of accountability for financial performance based on the calculation of model of accountability coefficient of financial performance of 4.445 sig value = 0.000 is greater than value = 0.05 because the significance value is greater than value = 0.05, hence the coefficient of accountability regression ((X2) affects positively and significantly towards financial performance (Y). Then H02 states that accountability is positively and significantly influential towards financial performance (Y) is acceptable.

Variable indicator (X2) accountability to variable Y (financial performance).

1) Accountability

Accountability should avoid the avoidance of budget that has been set to be honest and should be open quickly and appropriately to the community especially in the 10 OPD

2) Compliance

Must abide by the governance in the presentation of the regulatory report that has been established in order not to be misappropriated funds or budgets.

3) Avoidance

To avoid the name of the budget evasion on the community in order to observe a rule and law in force.

4) Policy

The trustees must obey the policies that have been set in order to be accountable to the public openly.

5) Openness

It must also provide information that is accurately and openly relevant to the community in order to access the information properly.

The results of the research in 10 OPD of Gorontalo must obey the governance in the presentation of financial statements in order to develop accountability of transparency and accountable financial performance in accordance with the expectations of society and (Stockholders).

Inter achievement of transparency and accountability to financial performance in 10 OPD must be able to be responsible in delivering information to the public or the public so that the community is biased to access information openly and relevant accurately For example, the supervision should be friendly in implementing how to access accurate data so that people are familiar with what is in the explanation.

The results of this study were not in line with research conducted by Sugiarto of accounting Department of Economics Faculty in Bandung year 2018 with the title of research ' ' Influence of government Accounting in order to build accountability, transparency and measuring the performance of regional governments ' ' research aims to find out if it can have significant positive effect on local government performance. For the government accounting standards should be a milestone in the inception of transparency, participation and accountability of the State in order to realize good

governance. Such strategic measures are required that need to be pursued and implemented together in the framework of the implementation of government accounting standards.

CONCLUSION

Transparency influence positive and significant to financial performance in 10 OPD Gorontalo City because of the public access to transparent in the completion of financial statements in addition to that also inform the Community and with information media that is easily accessible by the public is publicly relevant and accurate.

Accountability effect is positive and significant to the financial performance in which the management of financial statements is in accordance with procedure procedures in the planning, implementation and accountability of financial statements to be able to report an answer in the submission of financial statements to society or the public openly relevant and accurate and place of time.

Transparency and accountability impact positive and significant financial performance in order for the supervision of 10 OPD can comply with the ordinances and accountability in the completion of the report.

The results showed that Transparency and accountability effect positively and significantly on financial performance, both in partial and simultaneous, with large contributions from variables Independent of dependent variables, therefore it's advisable that the attention to transparency and accountability increasingly get the attention of the government as a decision maker in order to increase the regional financial performance

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